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Titel

Determination of dust sources using multiple correlations between the dust elements

Abstract

The south-western and western provinces of Iran are heavily affected by dust depositions. Besides the results of weathering and soil formation processes and the elemental composition of soil surfaces are influenced by aeolian dust transport and depositions. In most cases the source areas of the dust are not clear. After Geiger&Cooper 2010[1] it is possible to conclude the dust source areas from the dust elemental composition. Therefore this study's objective is the analysis of the elemental composition of dust samples, and their elemental correlations of 10 dust sampling stations in the South-West of Iran for the determination of the dust source areas. Monthly dust samples including event frequencies were collected in the provinces of Khuzestan, Khoramabad, and Kermanshah from south to west. The metal concentration of the dust was determined using inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS). Dust event frequency (DEF) was recorded daily based on its reduction of visibility in air and CCME standard (<1000m visibility for PM_{2.5}).

The association of daily data recorded from DEF together with result from the ICP-MS will be discussed. Strong positive correlation obtained between the amount of dust deposition and DEF in all samplers placed in south and west except one in Khoramabad with a lack of associations. Moreover, monthly element content in samples of each location with multi-DEF records has been driven separately; as a consequence we can better understand the individual association among the elements.

The positive correlation between DEF and classified metals[1,2] was significant ($P < 0.05$) for Na, Mg in a "geologic group", Zn in an organic group Ni, Mg in an industry group and Cd, Pb in the group of smelting plants. A strong negative correlation have been observed from the same classification significantly for Si, Ca, Sr in a "geologic group", Cr in an industry and As, Pb in smeltery. However, elements from organic group had no negative correlation with DEF.

The high negative correlation in this study can be described as that the metals in the dust can be originated from anthropogenic sources. So high correlation value indicates hazard associated with residing or conducting global, regional or local deposition sources and anthropogenic activities. Findings also argue that the major contributors of V, Cr, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, As, Se, Cd, Ba and Pb are in the ambient atmosphere and elements value were fluctuated from meteorological condition.

Literatur

[1] Geiger, Andrea and Cooper, John. (2010) Overview of airborne metals regulations, exposure limits, Health Effects, and Contemporary Research, US Environmental Protection Agency, Accessed on August, , Vol. 25, p. 2015.

[2] Janssen, CR et al. (2000) Uncertainties in the environmental risk assessment of metals, Human and Ecological Risk Assessment, Vol. 6, pp. 1003-1018.